

WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS AND SOCIALIZATION PROBLEMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8077496>

Abstract. *The trend of recent years is a sharp increase in the number of children with speech development disorders.*

Key words: *Speech disorders, speech, primary school children, socialization.*

РАБОТА С ДЕТЬМИ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ РЕЧИ И ПРОБЛЕМАМИ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ

Аннотация. *Тенденцией последних лет является резкое увеличение числа детей с нарушениями речевого развития.*

Ключевые слова: *Речевые нарушения, речь, дети младшего школьного возраста, социализация.*

To date, many children with speech disorders, due to unfavorable social and biological reasons, are brought up and trained in modern general education schools. Most of these children have difficulties during socialization.

A speech disorder is a deviation in the speaker's speech from the language norm established in a given language environment, manifested in partial disorders (sound reproduction, tempo, rhythm, voice, etc.) and pre-determined by disorders of the normal functioning of psychophysiological mechanisms of speech activity.

The degree of speech impairment plays a particularly significant role in the socialization of primary school children.

The development of a child's speech is a complex and lengthy process. The child learns to master the forms of the language in which he develops. The child begins his life path with a ready and complex language. To successfully communicate with the people around him, the child must be proficient in this language. With the help of the native language, the child establishes social contacts with adults and peers .

In children with speech disorders, communicative abilities are characterized by the fact that they often ignore the interlocutor, seek to speak out first of all, and not to tell anything. At the same time, it does not matter for them whether their story is clear to the interlocutor.

The low level of cognitive activity is manifested in the following: there is insufficient stability of attention, limited possibilities of its distribution, the volume decreases reproduction and memorization of the material. Verbal memory is reduced while maintaining logical and semantic memory. The productivity of memorization in children is also reduced. Difficulties in the development of serial organization of movements were revealed in this category of children. They forget the elements and the sequence of tasks, complex instructions. Processing of auditory information also causes great difficulties.

The peculiarities of the emotional – volitional sphere of this category of children with speech disorders are manifested in: irritability or general inhibition, increased excitability, tearfulness, multiple mood changes, insularity, touchiness.

The peculiarities of thinking are generated by the connection of speech disorders with other aspects of mental development. "Having the prerequisites for mastering mental operations

accessible to their age, children lag behind in the development of verbal and logical thinking, without special training they hardly master analysis and synthesis, comparison and generalization..."

In a comprehensive school, three groups of difficulties can be distinguished, which are observed in the process of socialization of primary school children with speech disorders:

1) difficulties caused by individual psychological characteristics (character, temperament, emotional states, etc.);

2) difficulties caused by social factors (minimum level of experience and information, communication problems among peers and adults, as well as features of the intra-classroom and intra-family climate);

3) difficulties associated with a deviation in speech development (various features of forms of communication, low speech activity, small volume of active and passive vocabulary, etc.).

The first group is difficulties that are associated with individual psychological characteristics. For example, if a child is irritable, short-tempered, not restrained, overly sensitive, weakly controlling his emotions, as well as with a prevailing bad mood, then in this case awareness of a speech disorder can lead to significant difficulties in establishing interpersonal contacts.

The second group is social factors that cause difficulties in the communication of younger schoolchildren with speech disorders. Social isolation causes great harm to the child's development. Parents do not always attach importance to communication with the child, so he does not receive the necessary skills of interaction in society.

The third group includes communication difficulties associated with speech underdevelopment. All types of speech disorders affect speech communication. This should be taken into account when planning correctional work to correct speech. However, work on overcoming speech disorders, unfortunately, does not solve all problems, related to the socialization of these children. Children with speech disorders of various etiologies have a lot in common. This brings them closer and makes them similar.

Many have pronunciation disorders, which makes their speech little understandable. Most children in this category have a small volume of active and passive vocabulary with a limited number of words that denote abstract and generalizing words. At the same time, there are no necessary communication skills, both with adults and peers. This greatly affects their mental and personal development.

One of the main prerequisites for the emergence of mental states, manifested in inadequate passivity, is the presence of various types of speech disorders in a child. These violations are an obstacle to the performance of certain tasks

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